

INTEGRATION OF TRADITIONAL AND MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING 2ND RHYTHM AWARENESS IN MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the integration of traditional pedagogical methods — Kodály, Orff Schulwerk, Dalcroze and Suzuki methods — and modern technologies and interactive approaches in teaching 2nd rhythm awareness to music education students. The effectiveness of the combined use of traditional methods and digital tools (Rhythmiq, Groove Scribe) for a deep understanding and consolidation of rhythm is highlighted. At the same time, students develop their musical skills in a creative and motivational way through game, improvisation and composition methods. The article emphasizes the joint importance of methods in learning 2nd rhythm in the process of music education and offers integrated approaches adapted to students.

Introduction. In music theory and practice, rhythm is a rhythmic part of music, which is formed by the repetition of various time units. In particular, rhythm 2 (binary rhythm) is a rhythmic unit consisting of two beats, which plays a key role in many musical genres. In the field of music, a clear sense and control of rhythm 2 serves as the foundation for mastering many complex rhythmic structures.

This article provides detailed information on the traditional methods widely used in teaching rhythm 2 - Kodály, Orff Schulwerk, Dalcroze, Suzuki - and the integration of modern technologies and creative approaches, and their importance in the educational process.

1. Traditional Methods: Basic Pedagogical Approaches

Kodály Method - The main idea of the Kodály Method is to learn the language of music as if you were learning your native language. In this method, rhythm is taught through speech and movement. For example, when teaching rhythm 2, counting the number of beats using hand movements or verbal repetition with students such as “tak-ta” is used. This approach is very important for internalizing and memorizing rhythm.[1]

In the Kodály Method, students are recommended to regularly repeat rhythmic exercises, combine hand and verbal expressions. In this method, the ability to control rhythm through movement is formed.

Orff Schulwerk - The Orff Method combines play, movement, music and dance, engaging students with music in an interactive way. In teaching rhythm 2, it is important to practice rhythmic structures using foot taps, clapping and other body movements in the Orff Method.[2]

Students will have the opportunity to better feel the rhythm of the 2nd rhythm through rhythmic games played in a group. This method encourages learning music in a lively and lively way.

Dalcroze Method - The Dalcroze Method encourages the feeling of rhythm through body movements. Students learn to control the 2nd rhythm through stepping, swinging, or other body movements. In this method, rhythm and movement complement each other, which allows for a deeper feeling of rhythm.

Recommendation for students: practice by moving different parts of the body rhythmically with the teacher.[3]

Suzuki Method - The Suzuki Method teaches music through listening and repetition. Before students start playing musical instruments, they pay great attention to hearing and mastering the rhythm. By correctly pronouncing the 2nd rhythm and listening to its different variations, the student increases rhythmic accuracy.

2. Modern technologies and interactive approaches.

Rhythmiq and Groove Scribe applications - As interactive tools suitable for students, applications such as Rhythmiq and Groove Scribe facilitate the study of rhythm. Through the Rhythmiq application, students can play various games and exercises related to rhythm 2, reinforcing rhythm using visual and audio cues.

Groove Scribe allows you to create, analyze and test rhythmic patterns. These tools allow students to independently learn and master rhythm.

Game methods - Students increase their interest in music by conducting rhythm exercises in a playful way. For example, by dancing or clapping with a group, it becomes natural to feel rhythm. This method is especially useful for young and inexperienced students.[4]

Improvisation and composition - Improvisation exercises for students provide an opportunity to independently learn and creatively apply rhythm. By creating short rhythmic improvisations based on rhythm 2, they will master rhythm more firmly.

Composition, on the other hand, provides an opportunity to systematically study rhythmic structures. By writing down and analyzing their rhythmic thoughts, students will gain a deeper understanding of the rhythmic rules of music.[5]

Integration and application in the educational process. The most effective approach for students is to combine traditional and modern methods. For example:

- Additional reinforcement of hand movements in the Kodály method with exercises in the Rhythmiq application.
- Conducting movement games in the Orff method in an interactive form on online platforms.
- Enriching body movements in the Dalcroze method with video lessons or VR technologies.
- Supplementing listening exercises in the Suzuki method with online audio materials.

This integration makes the learning process individual and interesting for students, leading them to a deeper understanding of rhythm.

Conclusion. While traditional methods of rhythm perception and learning — Kodály, Orff, Dalcroze, and Suzuki — form the foundation of education, modern technologies and

interactive methods further enrich this process. When used together, these approaches for students allow them to improve the quality of music education and create a creative and motivating environment.

Each student can find a comfortable and effective way to learn using these methods, not only to hear, but also to feel and creatively express rhythm.

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